

EFFECT OF FIBER VOLUME FRACTION AND MATERIAL HOMOGENEITY ON THE MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF RECYCLED WOVEN THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effect of fiber volume fraction (FVF) and material homogeneity on the mechanical performance of recycled woven thermoplastic composites. Recycling thermoplastic composites (TPCs) offers advantages over thermoset composites by enabling complete material recycling through melting and reshaping. The research utilized shredded 8-ply Toray Cetex 1100 C/PPS 5 harness satin woven composite mixed with neat PPS polymer at various ratios to achieve target FVFs of 16%, 20%, 25%, and 50%.

Processing was conducted using an internal mixer followed by compression molding into plates. Microstructural characterization was performed using optical microscopy and image analysis to quantify fiber volume fraction distribution and fiber bundle size. Samples were mechanically tested under tensile loading conditions.

Results demonstrate that dilution and mixing significantly improve fiber dispersion compared to unmixed material. The 50% FVF unmixed sample exhibited high stiffness but poor strength and ductility due to large undispersed fiber bundles. Lower FVF samples (16-25%) showed improved dispersion and mechanical performance, though with varying degrees of scatter. The 20% FVF sample demonstrated optimal balance of properties with good dispersion and reduced bundle sizes.

Image analysis successfully correlated microstructural features with mechanical performance, revealing that bundle size distribution and local FVF variations are critical factors affecting material strength. The study provides insights for optimizing recycling processes of aerospace-grade thermoplastic composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

The composites market has seen significant growth [1], with a corresponding increase in production and end-of-life waste. While thermoset-based composites are recycled on a small scale, focusing only on fiber recovery, thermoplastic-based composites (TPCs) offer a more comprehensive recycling solution. The thermoplastic polymer matrix allows for recycling the entire material through melting and reshaping, eliminating the need to separate fibers from the matrix.

A recycling approach for TPCs that has shown potential is schematically shown in Figure 1 [2]. The first step consists of mechanical recycling, by shredding the composite into flakes having a processable size (10 mm to 20 mm). Afterwards, the material can be diluted with additional polymer to facilitate compounding and then molding.

In the resulting discontinuous fiber reinforced recycled compound, significant attention is given to the fiber length, as it is an important factor influencing mechanical performance [3]. However, additional factors need to be considered, as they also contribute to the mechanical performance, such as fiber orientation and homogeneity of the fiber distribution.

A homogeneous distribution of the fibers in the polymer matrix is a critical factor in ensuring a high and consistent performance of both virgin and recycled composites. For short-fiber composites, homogeneity can be achieved relatively easily as standard mixing methods mix well but cause fiber breakage. For long fiber composites, heterogeneity is more pronounced, particularly when dealing with aerospace grade TPCs as the input material to be recycled has an initial high fiber volume fraction. Additionally, during the mixing process, the composite flake or tape structure needs to be disentangled to create a homogeneous material. A solution is to reduce the fiber fraction by incorporating additional polymer matrix during the mixing step [2]. This step is essential for distributing fibers evenly, significantly improving the uniformity of the final composite material.

In the recycling process the optimal final fiber volume fraction is not well defined at this point in time. In general, for virgin composites, it is well known that with low fiber volume fractions there is little reinforcement to ensure high mechanical performance. On the other hand, with high fiber volume fractions a drop in the material strength was observed when dealing with discontinuous fibers [4], [5]. This result suggests that other factors are limiting the performance at high fiber volume fraction. This indicates that more aspects need to be considered when recycling aerospace-grade composites, as they are characterized by a high fiber volume fraction, up to 60%.

Figure 1: Thermoplastic scrap processing cycle

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 MATERIALS & PROCESSING

The current study aims to investigate the recyclability of unidirectional and woven TPCs, understanding the effect of morphology of the recycled compound on the mechanical performance. The two components used in processing are shredded 8 ply thick consolidated laminates of Toray Cetex 1100 C/PPS 5 harness satin woven composite and for the matrix material Celanese Fortron 214 PPS is added.

Using an internal mixer, a Brabender Plastograph EC Plus W50 EHT measuring mixer, C/PPS scrap was compounded with different fractions of neat PPS as described in Table 1. All samples were processed for 5 minutes at 320°C and 5 RPM rotational speed, and a fill fraction of 0.7, occupying 35 ml of the available 50ml chamber. To create 50 grams of compounded composite material. Except for the undiluted scrap material of 50% FVF, which is intractable in the mixer and thus is compression molded as is.

Subsequently, these were compression molded at 50 bars of pressure into plates of dimensions 125 × 125 × 2 mm. Figure 2 shows the specimen layout. Each plate contains nine tensile specimens conforming to ISO 527-2-12A dimensions and was used for 16 micrographs. The tensile specimens were milled out of the plates.

Target FVF [%]	Fiber wt%	Mix time [min]	Additional polymer [wt%]
16	20	5	65%
20	25	5	56%
25	31	5	46%
50	57	0	0%

Table 1: Mixing parameters operated in the internal mixer.

For the microstructural characterization, the material in between the tensile bars was embedded in epoxy for polishing. For each imaging plane two areas (A and B as indicated in Figure 2) were imaged on a Keyence vhx-7000 optical microscope. Each image spans 5.4 x 2.1 mm at a resolution of 0.3 μm , resulting in 16 micrographs and an imaged area of 181.44 mm^2 per plate.

Tensile testing was performed in an Instron universal testing machine. Mechanical tests were performed at 23°C degrees and a constant crosshead displacement resulting in an engineering strain rate of $\dot{\epsilon} = 10^{-3}$. The strain was measured using an Instron AVE2 video extensometer with a gauge length of 20 mm.

Figure 2: Specimen dimensions and microscopy section planes

Figure 3: Example of the bundle triangulation of the 20% sample in location A-2

2.1 IMAGE PROCESSING & ANALYSIS

Image analysis of the fiber dispersion starts with identifying the locations of the fibers, subsequently the distribution is analyzed. As a first step, the image is binarized using the distinct peaks that are present in the image histogram. Each peak represents one of three components of the image, the mounting epoxy, the matrix material, and the fibers. A binary mask is constructed by taking the luminosity value in the middle of these peaks as the boundary. This binary map is used as the first check of the FVF by comparing the number of pixels assigned to the matrix and the fibers.

Second, the binary mask of the fiber locations is used to analyze the local fiber volume fraction. This method is based on analyzing the local fiber volume fraction compared to the mean fiber volume fraction. These steps are used to calculate the Intensity of segregation (IoS), as is used in analyzing mixtures in chemistry [6], [7]. However, on a pixel level the volume fraction is binary, therefore an averaging step is used at different cell sizes to get the local fiber volume fraction. The variance of the fiber volume fraction of the sample is divided by the variance of the fiber volume fraction before mixing. As 16 micrographs are analyzed per sample the IoS is calculated per micrograph and then averaged to get one IoS value for the sample. The spread of the IoS values within the sample can be used to show the bandwidth of the IoS.

Third, the fiber centers are analyzed using the MATLAB regionprops function, with the fiber centers a triangulation of the fiber centers is constructed. Then any links in the triangulation longer than three times the average fiber diameter are removed and any resulting links that are lines and do not form a

triangle are removed. The resulting triangulation corresponds to the bundles present in the composite. An example part of the triangulation is shown in figure 3. This process is analogous to the image analysis by Vincent et al [8].

3 RESULTS

The results are treated in the following order: first, the microstructure is discussed, then the image analysis results are treated, concluding with the mechanical results.

Figure 4: Cropped cross sections from the A-2 plane of all the samples having a global fiber volume fraction of (a) 16%, (b) 20%, (c) 25%, (d) 50%.

3.2 Microstructure

Figure 4 shows example cross sections of the plate specimens from plane 2 and location A as indicated in Figure 2. A first observation from the micrographs is that no voids could be found, indicating good consolidation. Second, the microstructure differs significantly. In Figure 4a of the 16% FVF specimen, both well dispersed fibers that have almost equal spacing to their neighbors exist, as well as the presence of a large undispersed fiber bundle originating from the 3K bundles present in the woven scrap material. A similar structure can be seen in the example of the 20% FVF sample, as well as undispersed bundles and dispersed individual fibers, a matrix-rich area is present in between two fiber bundles. By contrast the example of the 25% FVF sample shows only dispersed fibers and smaller fiber bundles. Lastly the unmixed 50% FVF specimen in Figure 4d shows stacks of fiber bundles with small resin rich areas and surprisingly small areas of dispersed fibers. Concluding, the microstructures of these materials show different characteristics depending on the fiber volume fraction. However, only qualitative information can be gathered directly from micrographs.

3.2 Image analysis

To validate the approach for thresholding the average volume fraction of each of the 16 micrographs per specimen is compared to the average volume fraction as is targeted through the compounding mixture.

Figure 5a shows the correlation between the input target FVF of the compounding process and the measured fiber volume fraction in the image analysis. First it is evident that the two measures of the fiber volume fraction agree quite well. Second, the lowest and highest FVF mixtures have a significantly higher spread in the fiber volume fraction.

Figure 5: (left) Relation of the fiber volume fraction from the input materials to the fiber volume fraction from the micrographs. (right) Distribution of the fibers present in the volume over the bundle size that contains them.

Figure 5b shows the distribution of the bundle sizes that the present fibers are contained within. It is evident that the dilution and mixing step result in a large change in the microstructure. This is well reflected in the change in the bundle size distribution from the 50% FVF sample compared to the mixed and diluted samples. Between the three diluted samples, the 16% FVF sample shows the largest remaining portion of large bundles. While the reduced bundle size of the 20% FVF samples indicates a good dispersion of the initial bundles.

Figure 6: IoS of the three mixed samples compared to the IoS of the unmixed 50% FVF samples (black) as a function of the averaging cell size. The areas contained by dashed lines indicate the bandwidth of the IoS.

The IoS of the three mixed samples are shown in Figure 6 and compared to the IoS of the unmixed sample. The value of the intensity of segregation relates to the variance of the fiber volume fraction. The 16% FVF sample shows an average IoS that is lower than the 50% FVF sample indicating some dispersion. But the bandwidth includes the whole range indicating that there are micrographs that have a similar variance in volume fraction as the unmixed 50% sample. All the way up to a low value of FVF. The 20% FVF sample has a lower average IoS and the maximum IoS is close to the mean of the unmixed 50% sample. Similarly, the 25% sample has a low average IoS and similar maximum values of IoS. However, the bandwidth is much lower.

Next to the fiber volume fraction, the fiber orientation in a specimen relates directly to the strength and stiffness of the material. After mixing the material is large in volume and during compression molding the height is reduced from 30mm to 2mm, meaning it is reasonable to assume a 2D random fiber orientation. However, it is good to check this assumption. By using the identified ellipses traced by the fibers in the cross sections the orientation in 3D can be determined. From these orientations an average orientation tensor can be constructed. The resulting tensors aligned with expectations for a 2D random case, showing diagonal components of 0.5 in the long directions of the plates. Only the 25% FVF sample showed a slight preferential orientation of 0.57 in the tensile direction and 0.34 perpendicular to it and 0.08 for the out of plane component.

3.3 Mechanical results

Aside from the fiber volume fraction and the fiber orientation, the fiber length is also of influence. It should be noted that only 50% FVF was not processed in the mixer and thus did not undergo a step where significant fiber attrition can occur. For these kind of fiber loadings and this type of mixer it has been reported that the weight average length is typically reduced to or below $500\mu\text{m}$ [9]. Therefore, the 50% FVF specimen has a significant advantage in fiber length compared to the other three samples.

Figure 7 shows the tensile curves for the different samples created. The scatter in results is evident from all the tensile curves. The bundle size distribution results are reflected in the large difference in performance between the mixed and diluted samples and the unmixed 50% FVF sample. The unmixed 50% FVF material has high stiffness but very poor strength and ductility. The 16% FVF sample that showed a spread in local FVF values from the image analysis and large remaining bundles also has a large spread in mechanical performance. So, the extremes of the samples show a correlation with the fiber bundle distribution and the local volume fraction.

The middle ground occupied by the FVF 20% and 25% samples show more subtle differences. The FVF 20% sample shows a large scatter in stiffness but a smaller scatter in strength, and most interesting two groups of failure strains. The FVF 25% by contrast, has a narrow distribution in stiffness but a large scatter in strength, but also shows the highest strength values of all specimens.

Figure 7: Tensile results of the reprocessed scrap materials

In conclusion, the performance of the material shows no trivial relationship between the fiber volume fraction and the resulting strength. However, at the high fiber volume fraction the performance is the worst even though that sample also has the highest fiber length, but the low homogeneity is likely inhibiting performance.

9 CONCLUSIONS

Using the current image analysis techniques, it is shown that the fiber volume fraction can be calculated quite accurately. Second, the bundle size distribution of the microstructure can provide a first indication towards the expected strength of the material. Interestingly, the sample with a high-volume fraction and the longest fiber length does not show the best performance. The benefits of dispersing and diluting woven composite scrap became evident in mechanical testing. Significant improvements in performance can be achieved by decreasing the fiber volume fraction and higher homogeneity could play a part in this relation.

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